

WAYS TO PRACTICE ORAL SPEAKING SKILLS

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ABSTRACT: *Language encompasses a range of aspects that enable individuals to communicate through diverse means. Discover the attributes and significance of verbal language, as well as the most prevalent ones. Verbal language refers to a language spoken using the vocal cords and hand gestures, both of which are widely utilized. Numerous features constitute spoken language, such as phonology, morphology, syntax, and pragmatics. Each of these elements plays a crucial role in how spoken language is used and comprehended.*

The aim of this article is to provide the production of speech appearance in the study of English as a language, through learning. providing methodical recommendations on the production and practical application of methods for ensuring freedom of speech and performing this task; providing information about the modern methods, methods and training manuals used today, giving them free speech and making methodological recommendations on the production and implementation of methods for the implementation of this task.

KEY WORDS: *english language, oral speech, methods, practice, improve, effective ways, independent learning.*

INTRODUCTION The teaching and learning of English as a foreign language has grown enormously. It has become a dominant language and almost billion of people are utilizing The English language as a convenient one for communicate orally or in written. More specifically, the focus has recently been on how to speak and use the language effectively¹.

Teaching oral language encompasses a range of factors, including the distinctions between spoken and written language. The primary purpose of language acquisition is to facilitate communication with others, which necessitates consideration of both speakers and listeners². Communication takes place within a social context, whether it is in a coffee shop, workplace, or classroom, and within a particular culture.

¹ Harmer, Jeremy, "The practice English language teaching"; London-New York; Longman,1991

² Gurrey P. Teaching English as a Foreign Language. – L.: Oxford, 2005. – 328 p.

Consequently, it is crucial to take into account the social and cultural context when speaking. How, then, can we teach oral language skills in light of these social and cultural factors? Rather than utilizing traditional methods of teaching oral English, discourse analysis offers a fresh approach to teaching and learning oral language. This approach concentrates on "the abilities required to put knowledge into practice and to achieve effective communication".

RESULTS There are some effective ways to improve speaking skills without a teacher or a partner that can significantly contribute to students' independent development.¹

Start thinking in English: Sometimes it is difficult for us to start speaking a foreign language, not because of the language itself, but because of the way we perceive it. If you think in your native language and try to speak in English, you always have to translate from one language to another. Translating is not as easy as it seems! Even those who are fluent in two or more languages sometimes have difficulty switching from one to the other.

Talk to yourself: When you are at home (or somewhere else, but alone) you can practice English with your favorite person: with you. If you're already thinking in English, try saying your thoughts out loud. Also read aloud. Practice is practice, and even if no one corrects your mistakes, you will become more confident in speaking English just by speaking your thoughts out loud.

Take advantage of the mirror: At any time of the day, take a few minutes to stand in front of a mirror and talk. Pick a topic, set a timer for 2-3 minutes, and just talk. The essence of this exercise is to follow the movements of your mouth, face and body language when you speak. You will also feel as if you are talking to someone, so imagine that you are having a conversation with a study partner. Talk for 2-3 minutes. Do not stop! If you stumble over an unfamiliar word, try rephrasing the thought. You can always look up this word in 2-3 minutes. So you will understand exactly what words or sentences you have difficulty with.

Focus on fluency, not grammar: When you speak English, how often do you stop? The more pauses you make, the less confident you sound and the less comfortable you feel. Try the mirror exercise we talked about above, but challenge yourself to learn how to speak without pauses and without hesitation on every word. This may mean that grammar may suffer, and there is nothing to worry about! If you set yourself the task of speaking fluently, even if not always correctly, you will still be understood and your speech will sound better. As you progress, you will replace incorrect grammar and add missing vocabulary anyway.

¹ <https://www.fluentu.com/blog/english-rus/%D1%83%D1>

Practice with tongue twisters: Tongue twisters are expressions that are difficult to pronounce quickly. Here is one example: “The thirty-three thieves thought that they thrilled the throne throughout Thursday”. Try to say it several times in a row! It is not simple. These language games will help you find the correct position of your lips and tongue, and even help you improve your pronunciation. You will find a collection of amazing tongue twisters here.

Listen and repeat: Do you watch TV series or YouTube videos in English? Improve your fluency with these activities. Choose a short clip from the video and repeat it line by line. Try to copy the tone, tempo, and even the accent. It’s okay if you miss a couple of words, the most important thing is to keep talking. Try to speak so that your speech sounds exactly like on the video. Fluent is a great way to practice listening comprehension and repetition. Fluent turns real-world videos like music videos, film trailers, news releases, and inspirational talks into personalized English lessons.

Sing along to English songs: By singing along to your favorite songs in English, you learn to speak more fluently. Rap is a great way to practice English as often the words are pronounced like normal sentences. However, rappers pronounce words faster! Some words generally sound like nonsense, but if you keep up with the rapper, then you are definitely on the right track to fluent speech!

Learn different forms of new words: Sometimes you can practice without even opening your mouth. It will be easier for you to speak if you start learning not one, but several forms for new words at once. You should try this practice when you are learning new words. For example, if you just learned the word write, you should also learn other forms of it, such as wrote and written. It is important to know how the word is used correctly in each sentence structure. This knowledge will help you when you start speaking. You won’t have to pause and remember different words, because you will know exactly when and which word to use.

Learn phrases, not single words: Here’s an even better idea: learn phrases, not just single words. You can use correct grammar and vocabulary, but your sentence may still sound strange to a native speaker, simply because it is not spoken that way. For example, you might say “how do you feel today?” and a native speaker is more likely to say “how’re you doing?” or “what’s up?”. Phrases and expressions will help you speak more naturally.

Learn the most common sayings: Take some time to analyze how you yourself speak your own language. Find out what the English equivalents are for the most commonly used words and phrases in your native language. This will help you speak English as well as your own language.

Prepare for certain situations: Are you learning English for something specific? Perhaps you are learning English to get a job in an English-speaking company? In this case, practice what will help you in the interview. Are you learning English to make friends in America? Then you need to learn a completely different language. Before you go where you need to speak English, you can practice your lines. If you are getting ready to go to a restaurant, what kind of conversations can be held in the restaurant? Answer any questions the waiter may ask you. Try talking about food and menus.

Relax! You can become either your best friend or your worst enemy when you learn how to speak fluently! We know it's not easy, but try to stop worrying about how you sound when you speak. Just relax! If you get stuck or confused, just take a deep breath and start over. Speak more slowly, if that makes it easier for you. Take your time, take a breather to think about your next offer. Do whatever you need to do to become more confident in speaking English.

Tell in English the story you heard in your native language: Here's a fun way for you to find out how good your English is: choose a story you know well and retell it in English. Remember to think in English when telling a story. Focus on speaking fluently, not perfectly. Say each sentence out loud to yourself. Even if there is no one around to speak English with, you can still learn to speak fluently and confidently in private.

CONCLUSION The development of speaking skills is a crucial aspect of second language learning. To enhance the speaking skills of students in ESL and EFL classrooms, educators should incorporate diverse, engaging, and distinctive techniques that are beneficial to their pupils. They should conduct each lesson with various speaking activities, which can greatly contribute to the development of basic interactive skills necessary for life. These activities make students more active in the learning process and, at the same time, make their learning more meaningful and enjoyable.

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